

1820 1840 1860 1880 1900 1920 1940 1960 1980 2000
proto Wuhan CTCTCGAATACCCAAAAGACGAAGTCAACATCAATATGGTGGTCTTAAATCTAAGAGACATGCCATATTTGGCATCTTTCTCCCAAGCTTTTGGTGAACCTGGAAAGCTTGATTAAGCAATTCACAAACAAATTTGACCTGGTGAATTTAAAGTACAAAAGAAAGC 1800
Translation ORF/CDS LLEILQKKEKVNINIVGDFKLNEEIAIILASFSASSTSAFVETVKGLDYKAFKQIVESCNGNFKVTKGKA 1758
proto Alpha LLEILQKKEKVNINIVGDFKLNEEIAIILASFSASSTSAFVETVKGLDYKAFKQIVESCNGNFKVTKGKA 1758
Translation ORF/CDS LLEILQKKEKVNINIVGDFKLNEEIAIILASFSASSTSAFVETVKGLDYKAFKQIVESCNGNFKVTKGKA 1775
proto Beta LLEILQKKEKVNINIVGDFKLNEEIAIILASFSASSTSAFVETVKGLDYKAFKQIVESCNGNFKVTKGKA 1775
Translation ORF/CDS LLEILQKKEKVNINIVGDFKLNEEIAIILASFSASSTSAFVETVKGLDYKAFKQIVESCNGNFKVTKGKA 1778
proto Gamma LLEILQKKEKVNINIVGDFKLNEEIAIILASFSASSTSAFVETVKGLDYKAFKQIVESCNGNFKVTKGKA 1758
Translation ORF/CDS LLEILQKKEKVNINIVGDFKLNEEIAIILASFSASSTSAFVETVKGLDYKAFKQIVESCNGNFKVTKGKA 1774
proto Lambda LLEILQKKEKVNINIVGDFKLNEEIAIILASFSASSTSAFVETVKGLDYKAFKQIVESCNGNFKVTKGKA 1758
Translation ORF/CDS LLEILQKKEKVNINIVGDFKLNEEIAIILASFSASSTSAFVETVKGLDYKAFKQIVESCNGNFKVTKGKA 1762
proto MuGH LLEILQKKEKVNINIVGDFKLNEEIAIILASFSASSTSAFVETVKGLDYKAFKQIVESCNGNFKVTKGKA 2000
Translation ORF/CDS LLEILQKKEKVNINIVGDFKLNEEIAIILASFSASSTSAFVETVKGLDYKAFKQIVESCNGNFKVTKGKA 1958
proto Alpha KKGAWNICEQKKSILSPLYAFASEAARVRSIFSRTLETAQNSVRVRLQKAAITLDDGTSQYSLRLID 1975
Translation ORF/CDS KKGAWNICEQKKSILSPLYAFASEAARVRSIFSRTLETAQNSVRVRLQKAAITLDDGTSQYSLRLID 1978
proto Beta KKGAWNICEQKKSILSPLYAFASEAARVRSIFSRTLETAQNSVRVRLQKAAITLDDGTSQYSLRLID 1978
Translation ORF/CDS KKGAWNICEQKKSILSPLYAFASEAARVRSIFSRTLETAQNSVRVRLQKAAITLDDGTSQYSLRLID 1978
proto Gamma KKGAWNICEQKKSILSPLYAFASEAARVRSIFSRTLETAQNSVRVRLQKAAITLDDGTSQYSLRLID 1974
Translation ORF/CDS KKGAWNICEQKKSILSPLYAFASEAARVRSIFSRTLETAQNSVRVRLQKAAITLDDGTSQYSLRLID 1958
proto Lambda KKGAWNICEQKKSILSPLYAFASEAARVRSIFSRTLETAQNSVRVRLQKAAITLDDGTSQYSLRLID 1962
Translation ORF/CDS KKGAWNICEQKKSILSPLYAFASEAARVRSIFSRTLETAQNSVRVRLQKAAITLDDGTSQYSLRLID 2200
proto Wuhan CTATCATGTCCACATCTGATTCGCTCAACAACTCTGTAATGGCCACATACAGCTGGTGTTCAGTCTGCTGGCAGCTCTTCTCCGCACTTCTGAACTCTGCAAAATCTGCTGGTCTTACGAGGCGCTATAACAACTAGATGAAATTCACAGCTCATTGATG 2000
Translation ORF/CDS A M M F T S D L A T N N L V M A Y I T G G V V Q L T S Q W L T N I F G T V Y E K L K P V L D W L E E K F K E G V E F L R D G W E I V 2158
proto Alpha A M M F T S D L A T N N L V M A Y I T G G V V Q L T S Q W L T N I F G T V Y E K L K P V L D W L E E K F K E G V E F L R D G W E I V 2175
Translation ORF/CDS A M M F T S D L A T N N L V M A Y I T G G V V Q L T S Q W L T N I F G T V Y E K L K P V L D W L E E K F K E G V E F L R D G W E I V 2178
proto Beta A M M F T S D L A T N N L V M A Y I T G G V V Q L T S Q W L T N I F G T V Y E K L K P V L D W L E E K F K E G V E F L R D G W E I V 2158
Translation ORF/CDS A M M F T S D L A T N N L V M A Y I T G G V V Q L T S Q W L T N I F G T V Y E K L K P V L D W L E E K F K E G V E F L R D G W E I V 2174
proto Gamma A M M F T S D L A T N N L V M A Y I T G G V V Q L T S Q W L T N I F G T V Y E K L K P V L D W L E E K F K E G V E F L R D G W E I V 2158
Translation ORF/CDS A M M F T S D L A T N N L V M A Y I T G G V V Q L T S Q W L T N I F G T V Y E K L K P V L D W L E E K F K E G V E F L R D G W E I V 2162
proto Omicron A M M F T S D L A T N N L V M A Y I T G G V V Q L T S Q W L T N I F G T V Y E K L K P V L D W L E E K F K E G V E F L R D G W E I V 2162
Translation ORF/CDS A M M F T S D L A T N N L V M A Y I T G G V V Q L T S Q W L T N I F G T V Y E K L K P V L D W L E E K F K E G V E F L R D G W E I V 2400
proto Wuhan AAATTTATCCAACTGCTGTAAGATTCGGTGGCAAAATTCACCTCTCAAAGCAAAATTAAGCAGAGTCTCAGACATCTTAAAGCTGTAATAAATTTGGCTTGTGCTGACTCTACATTATGTTGGTGAACCTAAACTAAAGCTTGAATTTAGGTAAGCAATTTGCAGCCTCAAAGGAT 2400
Translation ORF/CDS K F I S T C A C E I V G G Q I V T C A K E I K E S V Q T F F K L V N K F L A L C A D S I I I G G A K L K A L N L G E T F V T H S K G L 2358
proto Alpha K F I S T C A C E I V G G Q I V T C A K E I K E S V Q T F F K L V N K F L A L C A D S I I I G G A K L K A L N L G E T F V T H S K G L 2358
Translation ORF/CDS K F I S T C A C E I V G G Q I V T C A K E I K E S V Q T F F K L V N K F L A L C A D S I I I G G A K L K A L N L G E T F V T H S K G L 2375
proto Beta K F I S T C A C E I V G G Q I V T C A K E I K E S V Q T F F K L V N K F L A L C A D S I I I G G A K L K A L N L G E T F V T H S K G L 2378
Translation ORF/CDS K F I S T C A C E I V G G Q I V T C A K E I K E S V Q T F F K L V N K F L A L C A D S I I I G G A K L K A L N L G E T F V T H S K G L 2378
proto Gamma K F I S T C A C E I V G G Q I V T C A K E I K E S V Q T F F K L V N K F L A L C A D S I I I G G A K L K A L N L G E T F V T H S K G L 2374
Translation ORF/CDS K F I S T C A C E I V G G Q I V T C A K E I K E S V Q T F F K L V N K F L A L C A D S I I I G G A K L K A L N L G E T F V T H S K G L 2358
proto MuGH K F I S T C A C E I V G G Q I V T C A K E I K E S V Q T F F K L V N K F L A L C A D S I I I G G A K L K A L N L G E T F V T H S K G L 2362
Translation ORF/CDS K F I S T C A C E I V G G Q I V T C A K E I K E S V Q T F F K L V N K F L A L C A D S I I I G G A K L K A L N L G E T F V T H S K G L 2600
proto Wuhan GTACAGAAAGTCTGTAATCCAGAGAAAGTCCGCTACTCGCTCAAAGCCCAAAGAAATATCTCTTAAAGGAGAAACACTCCACAGAAAGTTCACAGAGAAAGTCTGTTGAAAGCTGCTATTACAACTTAGAACCCTACTAGTAGAGCTTGAAGCTCCGATGGTGGTACACAC 2600
Translation ORF/CDS Y R K C V K S R E E T G L L M P L K A P K E I I F L E G E T L P T E V L T E E V V L K T G D L Q P L E Q P T S E A V E A P L V G T P 2558
proto Alpha Y R K C V K S R E E T G L L M P L K A P K E I I F L E G E T L P T E V L T E E V V L K T G D L Q P L E Q P T S E A V E A P L V G T P 2575
Translation ORF/CDS Y R K C V K S R E E T G L L M P L K A P K E I I F L E G E T L P T E V L T E E V V L K T G D L Q P L E Q P T S E A V E A P L V G T P 2578
proto Beta Y R K C V K S R E E T G L L M P L K A P K E I I F L E G E T L P T E V L T E E V V L K T G D L Q P L E Q P T S E A V E A P L V G T P 2558
Translation ORF/CDS Y R K C V K S R E E T G L L M P L K A P K E I I F L E G E T L P T E V L T E E V V L K T G D L Q P L E Q P T S E A V E A P L V G T P 2574
proto Gamma Y R K C V K S R E E T G L L M P L K A P K E I I F L E G E T L P T E V L T E E V V L K T G D L Q P L E Q P T S E A V E A P L V G T P 2558
Translation ORF/CDS Y R K C V K S R E E T G L L M P L K A P K E I I F L E G E T L P T E V L T E E V V L K T G D L Q P L E Q P T S E A V E A P L V G T P 2562
proto Omicron Y R K C V K S R E E T G L L M P L K A P K E I I F L E G E T L P T E V L T E E V V L K T G D L Q P L E Q P T S E A V E A P L V G T P 2562
Translation ORF/CDS Y R K C V K S R E E T G L L M P L K A P K E I I F L E G E T L P T E V L T E E V V L K T G D L Q P L E Q P T S E A V E A P L V G T P 2800
proto Wuhan TTTGATCAACGGCTGTGCTCGAATCAAGACAGAAAGTCTGGCCCTGCACCTAATATGATGTAACAACAACTCCACACTAAAGGCTGCCACCAAAAGTACTTGGTGATGACACTGTAGTAGAGCTGCAAGCTTGAATGACATTTGATGAGCTGGATGAAAT 2800
Translation ORF/CDS V C I N G L M L L L E I K D T E K Y C A L A P N M M V T N N T F T L K G G A P T K V T F G D D T V I E V Q G Y K S V N I T F E L D E R I 2758
proto Alpha V C I N G L M L L L E I K D T E K Y C A L A P N M M V T N N T F T L K G G A P T K V T F G D D T V I E V Q G Y K S V N I T F E L D E R I 2775
Translation ORF/CDS V C I N G L M L L L E I K D T E K Y C A L A P N M M V T N N T F T L K G G A P T K V T F G D D T V I E V Q G Y K S V N I T F E L D E R I 2778
proto Beta V C I N G L M L L L E I K D T E K Y C A L A P N M M V T N N T F T L K G G A P T K V T F G D D T V I E V Q G Y K S V N I T F E L D E R I 2758
Translation ORF/CDS V C I N G L M L L L E I K D T E K Y C A L A P N M M V T N N T F T L K G G A P T K V T F G D D T V I E V Q G Y K S V N I T F E L D E R I 2774
proto Gamma V C I N G L M L L L E I K D T E K Y C A L A P N M M V T N N T F T L K G G A P T K V T F G D D T V I E V Q G Y K S V N I T F E L D E R I 2758
Translation ORF/CDS V C I N G L M L L L E I K D T E K Y C A L A P N M M V T N N T F T L K G G A P T K V T F G D D T V I E V Q G Y K S V N I T F E L D E R I 2762
proto Omicron V C I N G L M L L L E I K D T E K Y C A L A P N M M V T N N T F T L K G G A P T K V T F G D D T V I E V Q G Y K S V N I T F E L D E R I 2800
Translation ORF/CDS V C I N G L M L L L E I K D T E K Y C A L A P N M M V T N N T F T L K G G A P T K V T F G D D T V I E V Q G Y K S V N I T F E L D E R I 3000
proto Wuhan GATAAGACTTAATGAGAACTGCTCGCTACATGCACTCGGTACAGAAAGTAAATGAGTCCGCTGTTGGCAGACTGCTCATAAAACCTTCCACCAAGCTTCTGAACTTACCACTGGGCTGATTTAGTAGAGTGGAGTACTGCTCATCTACTACTTATGATGAGCTGGATGAAAT 3000
Translation ORF/CDS D K V L N E K C S A Y T V E L G T E V N E F A C V V A D A V I K T L Q P V S E L L T P L G I D L D E W S M A T Y Y L F D E S G E F K L 2958
proto Alpha D K V L N E K C S A Y T V E L G T E V N E F A C V V A D A V I K T L Q P V S E L L T P L G I D L D E W S M A T Y Y L F D E S G E F K L 2975
Translation ORF/CDS D K V L N E K C S A Y T V E L G T E V N E F A C V V A D A V I K T L Q P V S E L L T P L G I D L D E W S M A T Y Y L F D E S G E F K L 2978
proto Beta D K V L N E K C S A Y T V E L G T E V N E F A C V V A D A V I K T L Q P V S E L L T P L G I D L D E W S M A T Y Y L F D E S G E F K L 2958
Translation ORF/CDS D K V L N E K C S A Y T V E L G T E V N E F A C V V A D A V I K T L Q P V S E L L T P L G I D L D E W S M A T Y Y L F D E S G E F K L 2974
proto Gamma D K V L N E K C S A Y T V E L G T E V N E F A C V V A D A V I K T L Q P V S E L L T P L G I D L D E W S M A T Y Y L F D E S G E F K L 2958
Translation ORF/CDS D K V L N E K C S A Y T V E L G T E V N E F A C V V A D A V I K T L Q P V S E L L T P L G I D L D E W S M A T Y Y L F D E S G E F K L 2962
proto Omicron D K V L N E K C S A Y T V E L G T E V N E F A C V V A D A V I K T L Q P V S E L L T P L G I D L D E W S M A T Y Y L F D E S G E F K L 3000
Translation ORF/CDS D K V L N E K C S A Y T V E L G T E V N E F A C V V A D A V I K T L Q P V S E L L T P L G I D L D E W S M A T Y Y L F D E S G E F K L 3180
proto Wuhan GCCTCACAATGTATTGTTCTTCTACCTCCAGATGAGTCAAGAAAGGCTGTTGGAAGAAGACTTGGACTCAATCAATGACTGCTGAGATGATACCAAGTAACTTTGGAAATTTGCCACTTCTGCTCTTCAACTCAAGAAAGCAAGAAAGTTGATGATG 3200
Translation ORF/CDS A S H M Y C S F Y P P D E D E E E G D C E E E E F E P S T Q Y E Y G T E D D Y Q G K P L E F G A T S A A L Q P E E E Q E E D W L D D 3158
proto Alpha A S H M Y C S F Y P P D E D E E E G D C E E E E F E P S T Q Y E Y G T E D D Y Q G K P L E F G A T S A A L Q P E E E Q E E D W L D D 3175
Translation ORF/CDS A S H M Y C S F Y P P D E D E E E G D C E E E E F E P S T Q Y E Y G T E D D Y Q G K P L E F G A T S A A L Q P E E E Q E E D W L D D 3178
proto Beta A S H M Y C S F Y P P D E D E E E G D C E E E E F E P S T Q Y E Y G T E D D Y Q G K P L E F G A T S A A L Q P E E E Q E E D W L D D 3158
Translation ORF/CDS A S H M Y C S F Y P P D E D E E E G D C E E E E F E P S T Q Y E Y G T E D D Y Q G K P L E F G A T S A A L Q P E E E Q E E D W L D D 3174
proto Gamma A S H M Y C S F Y P P D E D E E E G D C E E E E F E P S T Q Y E Y G T E D D Y Q G K P L E F G A T S A A L Q P E E E Q E E D W L D D 3158
Translation ORF/CDS A S H M Y C S F Y P P D E D E E E G D C E E E E F E P S T Q Y E Y G T E D D Y Q G K P L E F G A T S A A L Q P E E E Q E E D W L D D 3162
proto Omicron A S H M Y C S F Y P P D E D E E E G D C E E E E F E P S T Q Y E Y G T E D D Y Q G K P L E F G A T S A A L Q P E E E Q E E D W L D D 3162
Translation ORF/CDS A S H M Y C S F Y P P D E D E E E G D C E E E E F E P S T Q Y E Y G T E D D Y Q G K P L E F G A T S A A L Q P E E E Q E E D W L D D 3162

3220 3240 3260 3280 3300 3320 3340 3360 3380 3400
proto Wuhan ATAGTCAACAACCTGGTTCACCAACAGCGAGTGGACCAACACACACTACTTCAACAATGTTGAGGTTCAACTCAATAGAGATGGAACTTACACCGTTTGCACATTTGAAGTGAATGTTTGGTATTAAACACTGACGAATGTATACATATAAATGGACACACTTGGCAAGACT 3400
Translation ORF/CD5 D S Q Q T V G Q Q D G S E D N Q T T T I Q T I V E V Q P Q L E M E L T P V V Q T I E V N S F S G Y L K L T D N V Y I K N A D I V E E A
proto Alpha
Translation ORF/CD5 D S Q Q T V G Q Q D G S E D N Q T T T I Q T I V E V Q P Q L E M E L T P V V Q T I E V N S F S G Y L K L T D N V Y I K N A D I V E E A 3358
proto Beta
Translation ORF/CD5 D S Q Q T V G Q Q D G S E D N Q T T T I Q T I V E V Q P Q L E M E L T P V V Q T I E V N S F S G Y L K L T D N V Y I K N A D I V E E A 3375
proto Gamma
Translation ORF/CD5 D S Q Q T V G Q Q D G S E D N Q T T T I Q T I V E V Q P Q L E M E L T P V V Q T I E V N S F S G Y L K L T D N V Y I K N A D I V E E A 3378
proto Delta
Translation ORF/CD5 D S Q Q T V G Q Q D G S E D N Q T T T I Q T I V E V Q P Q L E M E L T P V V Q T I E V N S F S G Y L K L T D N V Y I K N A D I V E E A 3358
proto Lambda
Translation ORF/CD5 D S Q Q T V G Q Q D G S E D N Q T T T I Q T I V E V Q P Q L E M E L T P V V Q T I E V N S F S G Y L K L T D N V Y I K N A D I V E E A 3374
proto MuGH
Translation ORF/CD5 D S Q Q T V G Q Q D G S E D N Q T T T I Q T I V E V Q P Q L E M E L T P V V Q T I E V N S F S G Y L K L T D N V Y I K N A D I V E E A 3358
proto Omicron
Translation ORF/CD5 D S Q Q T V G Q Q D G S E D N Q T T T I Q T I V E V Q P Q L E M E L T P V V Q T I E V N S F S G Y L K L T D N V Y I K N A D I V E E A 3362
3420 3440 3460 3480 3500 3520 3540 3560 3580 3600
proto Wuhan AAAAGGTAAACCAACCTGGTTCATTCAGCAGCAATGTTTACCTTAAACATGGAGAGCTGTTCCAGAGCTTAAATAGGCTACTAACATGCCATCGAAGTGAATCGATGATACATAGCTAATGACACACTAAAGTGGTGGTATGTTGTTTAAAGCGACACACTTCTGCTAAACACTGTTCTCA 3600
Translation ORF/CD5 K K V K P T V V V N A A N V Y L K H G G G V A G A L N K A T N N A M Q V E S D D Y I A T N G P L K V G G S C V L S G H N L A K H C L H
proto Alpha
Translation ORF/CD5 K K V K P T V V V N A A N V Y L K H G G G V A G A L N K A T N N A M Q V E S D D Y I A T N G P L K V G G S C V L S G H N L A K H C L H 3558
proto Beta
Translation ORF/CD5 K K V K P T V V V N A A N V Y L K H G G G V A G A L N K A T N N A M Q V E S D D Y I A T N G P L K V G G S C V L S G H N L A K H C L H 3575
proto Gamma
Translation ORF/CD5 K K V K P T V V V N A A N V Y L K H G G G V A G A L N K A T N N A M Q V E S D D Y I A T N G P L K V G G S C V L S G H N L A K H C L H 3578
proto Delta
Translation ORF/CD5 K K V K P T V V V N A A N V Y L K H G G G V A G A L N K A T N N A M Q V E S D D Y I A T N G P L K V G G S C V L S G H N L A K H C L H 3558
proto Lambda
Translation ORF/CD5 K K V K P T V V V N A A N V Y L K H G G G V A G A L N K A T N N A M Q V E S D D Y I A T N G P L K V G G S C V L S G H N L A K H C L H 3574
proto MuGH
Translation ORF/CD5 K K V K P T V V V N A A N V Y L K H G G G V A G A L N K A T N N A M Q V E S D D Y I A T N G P L K V G G S C V L S G H N L A K H C L H 3558
proto Omicron
Translation ORF/CD5 K K V K P T V V V N A A N V Y L K H G G G V A G A L N K A T N N A M Q V E S D D Y I A T N G P L K V G G S C V L S G H N L A K H C L H 3562
3660 3680 3700 3720 3740 3760 3780 3800 3820 3840 3860 3880 3900 3920 3940 3960 4000
proto Wuhan TGTTCGGCCCAATCTTAAACAAGCTGAAGCACTCACTCTTAAGACTGCTTAAATAATTTTAAACAGCAACTTCTACTGGCAACTATTTCACCTGGTATTTTGGTGTACCTATACATCTTAAAGACTGTTCCAGCAACTGCTACTACTGCTGTTGTAATAAATCTCT 3800
Translation ORF/CD5 V V G P N V N K G E D I Q L L K S A Y E N F N Q H E V L L A P L L S A G I F G A D P I H S L R V C V D T V R T N V Y L A V F D K N L
proto Alpha
Translation ORF/CD5 V V G P N V N K G E D I Q L L K S A Y E N F N Q H E V L L A P L L S A G I F G A D P I H S L R V C V D T V R T N V Y L A V F D K N L 3758
proto Beta
Translation ORF/CD5 V V G P N V N K G E D I Q L L K S A Y E N F N Q H E V L L A P L L S A G I F G A D P I H S L R V C V D T V R T N V Y L A V F D K N L 3775
proto Gamma
Translation ORF/CD5 V V G P N V N K G E D I Q L L K S A Y E N F N Q H E V L L A P L L S A G I F G A D P I H S L R V C V D T V R T N V Y L A V F D K N L 3778
proto Delta
Translation ORF/CD5 V V G P N V N K G E D I Q L L K S A Y E N F N Q H E V L L A P L L S A G I F G A D P I H S L R V C V D T V R T N V Y L A V F D K N L 3758
proto Lambda
Translation ORF/CD5 V V G P N V N K G E D I Q L L K S A Y E N F N Q H E V L L A P L L S A G I F G A D P I H S L R V C V D T V R T N V Y L A V F D K N L 3774
proto MuGH
Translation ORF/CD5 V V G P N V N K G E D I Q L L K S A Y E N F N Q H E V L L A P L L S A G I F G A D P I H S L R V C V D T V R T N V Y L A V F D K N L 3758
proto Omicron
Translation ORF/CD5 V V G P N V N K G E D I Q L L K S A Y E N F N Q H E V L L A P L L S A G I F G A D P I H S L R V C V D T V R T N V Y L A V F D K N L 3762
3920 3940 3960 3980 4000 4020 4040 4060 4080 4100 4120 4140 4160 4180 4200
proto Wuhan ATGCAACAACCTGTTTCAAGCTTTTGAAGTGAAGACTGAAACAAGCTGAAACAAGACTGCTGAGACTTCTAAAGAGCAACTTAACTGAAAGTAACTTCACTGAAAGCAAGCAAGTGAAGAAATCAAGACTGTAAGAAATCAAGACTGTTGTAAGAAAGTAAACAACAACCTGGAAGAAACTAACTGCT 4000
Translation ORF/CD5 Y D K L V S S F L E M K S E K Q V E Q K I A E I P K E E V K P F I T E S K P S V E Q R K Q D D K K I K A C V E E V T T T L E E T K F L
proto Alpha
Translation ORF/CD5 Y D K L V S S F L E M K S E K Q V E Q K I A E I P K E E V K P F I T E S K P S V E Q R K Q D D K K I K A C V E E V T T T L E E T K F L 3958
proto Beta
Translation ORF/CD5 Y D K L V S S F L E M K S E K Q V E Q K I A E I P K E E V K P F I T E S K P S V E Q R K Q D D K K I K A C V E E V T T T L E E T K F L 3975
proto Gamma
Translation ORF/CD5 Y D K L V S S F L E M K S E K Q V E Q K I A E I P K E E V K P F I T E S K P S V E Q R K Q D D K K I K A C V E E V T T T L E E T K F L 3978
proto Delta
Translation ORF/CD5 Y D K L V S S F L E M K S E K Q V E Q K I A E I P K E E V K P F I T E S K P S V E Q R K Q D D K K I K A C V E E V T T T L E E T K F L 3958
proto Lambda
Translation ORF/CD5 Y D K L V S S F L E M K S E K Q V E Q K I A E I P K E E V K P F I T E S K P S V E Q R K Q D D K K I K A C V E E V T T T L E E T K F L 3974
proto MuGH
Translation ORF/CD5 Y D K L V S S F L E M K S E K Q V E Q K I A E I P K E E V K P F I T E S K P S V E Q R K Q D D K K I K A C V E E V T T T L E E T K F L 3958
proto Omicron
Translation ORF/CD5 Y D K L V S S F L E M K S E K Q V E Q K I A E I P K E E V K P F I T E S K P S V E Q R K Q D D K K I K A C V E E V T T T L E E T K F L 3962
4020 4040 4060 4080 4100 4120 4140 4160 4180 4200
proto Wuhan ACAGAAAACCTGTTACTTTATAGCAATAGCAACTCTTATCAGACTGCTGAGTGTGACACTGACACTCTTTTAAAGAAAGTGGTCCATATATAGTGGTCACTGTTTCAAGAGGTTTAACTGCTGGTATACACTAAAGAGGCTGGTCAACTGAAATGCTAGCAAGCA 4200
Translation ORF/CD5 T E N L L L Y I D I N G N L H P D S A T L V S D I D I T F L K K D A P Y I V G D V V Q E G V L T A V V I P T K K A G G T T E M L A K A
proto Alpha
Translation ORF/CD5 T E N L L L Y I D I N G N L H P D S A T L V S D I D I T F L K K D A P Y I V G D V V Q E G V L T A V V I P T K K A G G T T E M L A K A 4158
proto Beta
Translation ORF/CD5 T E N L L L Y I D I N G N L H P D S A T L V S D I D I T F L K K D A P Y I V G D V V Q E G V L T A V V I P T K K A G G T T E M L A K A 4175
proto Gamma
Translation ORF/CD5 T E N L L L Y I D I N G N L H P D S A T L V S D I D I T F L K K D A P Y I V G D V V Q E G V L T A V V I P T K K A G G T T E M L A K A 4178
proto Delta
Translation ORF/CD5 T E N L L L Y I D I N G N L H P D S A T L V S D I D I T F L K K D A P Y I V G D V V Q E G V L T A V V I P T K K S G G T T E M L A K A 4158
proto Lambda
Translation ORF/CD5 T E N L L L Y I D I N G N L H P D S A T L V S D I D I T F L K K D A P Y I V G D V V Q E G V L T A V V I P T K K A G G T T E M L A K A 4174
proto MuGH
Translation ORF/CD5 T E N L L L Y I D I N G N L H P D S A T L V S D I D I T F L K K D A P Y I V G D V V Q E G V L T A V V I P T K K A G G T T E M L A K A 4158
proto Omicron
Translation ORF/CD5 T E N L L L Y I D I N G N L H P D S A T L V S D I D I T F L K K D A P Y I V G D V V Q E G V L T A V V I P T K K A G G T T E M L A K A 4162
4220 4240 4260 4280 4300 4320 4340 4360 4380 4400
proto Wuhan TTGCAACCCAGCAACCAATATATAACCACTACCGGTCAGGTTTAAAGTGTACACTGAGAGAGGCAAGCACTGCTTAAAGACTGAAAGTGCCTTACACTTACACTTATATCTCTAATGAGCAAGCAAGAACTTGGAACTGTTTGGAAATGGCAAGTGGTCCACATGCGAC 4400
Translation ORF/CD5 L R K V P T D N Y I T T Y P G Q G L N G Y T V E E A K T V L K K C K S A F Y I L P S I I S N E K Q E I L G T V S W N L R E M L A H A
proto Alpha
Translation ORF/CD5 L R K V P T D N Y I T T Y P G Q G L N G Y T V E E A K T V L K K C K S A F Y I L P S I I S N E K Q E I L G T V S W N L R E M L A H A 4358
proto Beta
Translation ORF/CD5 L R K V P T D N Y I T T Y P G Q G L N G Y T V E E A K T V L K K C K S A F Y I L P S I I S N E K Q E I L G T V S W N L R E M L A H A 4375
proto Gamma
Translation ORF/CD5 L R K V P T D N Y I T T Y P G Q G L N G Y T V E E A K T V L K K C K S A F Y I L P S I I S N E K Q E I L G T V S W N L R E M L A H A 4378
proto Delta
Translation ORF/CD5 L R K V P T D N Y I T T Y P G Q G L N G Y T V E E A K T V L K K C K S A F Y I L P S I I S N E K Q E I L G T V S W N L R E M L A H A 4358
proto Lambda
Translation ORF/CD5 L R K V P T D N Y I T T Y P G Q G L N G Y T V E E A K T V L K K C K S A F Y I L P S I I S N E K Q E I L G T V S W N L R E M L A H A 4374
proto MuGH
Translation ORF/CD5 L R K V P T D N Y I T T Y P G Q G L N G Y T V E E A K T V L K K C K S A F Y I L P S I I S N E K Q E I L G T V S W N L R E M L A H A 4358
proto Omicron
Translation ORF/CD5 L R K V P T D N Y I T T Y P G Q G L N G Y T V E E A K T V L K K C K S A F Y I L P S I I S N E K Q E I L G T V S W N L R E M L A H A 4362
4420 4440 4460 4480 4500 4520 4540 4560 4580 4600
proto Wuhan AAGAACAACCCCAATTAAGCTCTGCTGCGAAGTAAAGCTAGTTCACACTACAGCGTAAATATAAGGTTTAAAGTAAACAAGAGGCTGGTGGTATGCTGAGTATTTTACACCACTAAACAACACTAGGCTCACTCAACCACTAAAGTGAACACTTCTGCAATGCGCA 4600
Translation ORF/CD5 E E T R K L M P V C V E T K A I V S T I Q R K Y K G I K I Q E G V V D Y G A R F Y F Y T S K T T V A S L I N T L N D L N E T L V T M P
proto Alpha
Translation ORF/CD5 E E T R K L M P V C V E T K A I V S T I Q R K Y K G I K I Q E G V V D Y G A R F Y F Y T S K T T V A S L I N T L N D L N E T L V T M P 4558
proto Beta
Translation ORF/CD5 E E T R K L M P V C V E T K A I V S T I Q R K Y K G I K I Q E G V V D Y G A R F Y F Y T S K T T V A S L I N T L N D L N E T L V T M P 4575
proto Gamma
Translation ORF/CD5 E E T R K L M P V C V E T K A I V S T I Q R K Y K G I K I Q E G V V D Y G A R F Y F Y T S K T T V A S L I N T L N D L N E T L V T M P 4578
proto Delta
Translation ORF/CD5 E E T R K L M P V C V E T K A I V S T I Q R K Y K G I K I Q E G V V D Y G A R F Y F Y T S K T T V A S L I N T L N D L N E T L V T M P 4558
proto Lambda
Translation ORF/CD5 E E T R K L M P V C V E T K A I V S T I Q R K Y K G I K I Q E G V V D Y G A R F Y F Y T S K T T V A S L I N T L N D L N E T L V T M P 4574
proto MuGH
Translation ORF/CD5 E E T R K L M P V C V E T K A I V S T I Q R K Y K G I K I Q E G V V D Y G A R F Y F Y T S K T T V A S L I N T L N D L N E T L V T M P 4558
proto Omicron
Translation ORF/CD5 E E T R K L M P V C V E T K A I V S T I Q R K Y K G I K I Q E G V V D Y G A R F Y F Y T S K T T V A S L I N T L N D L N E T L V T M P 4562
4620 4640 4660 4680 4700 4720 4740 4760 4780 4800
proto Wuhan CTGCTTACTTAAACATGCTTAAAGCAAGCTCGGTATATACACTCTTAAAGTGCACACTGCTTCTTCTGCTGATGCTTACACGGTAAAGTGTATCTTCTCTTCTTAAAGCACTGAAGCAACTTTTAAACAACACTCACTGCTGCTTCTGTAAGAAATGCTGCTCA 4800
Translation ORF/CD5 L G Y V T H G L N L E E A A R Y M R S L K V P A T V S V S S P D A V T A Y N G Y L T S S S K T P E E H F I E T I S L A G S Y K D W S Y
proto Alpha
Translation ORF/CD5 L G Y V T H G L N L E E A A R Y M R S L K V P A T V S V S S P D A V T A Y N G Y L T S S S K T P E E H F I E T I S L A G S Y K D W S Y 4758
proto Beta
Translation ORF/CD5 L G Y V T H G L N L E E A A R Y M R S L K V P A T V S V S S P D A V T A Y N G Y L T S S S K T P E E H F I E T I S L A G S Y K D W S Y 4775
proto Gamma
Translation ORF/CD5 L G Y V T H G L N L E E A A R Y M R S L K V P A T V S V S S P D A V T A Y N G Y L T S S S K T P E E H F I E T I S L A G S Y K D W S Y 4778
proto Delta
Translation ORF/CD5 L G Y V T H G L N L E E A A R Y M R S L K V P A T V S V S S P D A V T A Y N G Y L T S S S K T P E E H F I E T I S L A G S Y K D W S Y 4758
proto Lambda
Translation ORF/CD5 L G Y V T H G L N L E E A A R Y M R S L K V P A T V S V S S P D A V T A Y N G Y L T S S S K T P E E H F I E T I S L A G S Y K D W S Y 4774
proto MuGH
Translation ORF/CD5 L G Y V T H G L N L E E A A R Y M R S L K V P A T V S V S S P D A V T A Y N G Y L T S S S K T P E E H F I E T I S L A G S Y K D W S Y 4758
proto Omicron
Translation ORF/CD5 L G Y V T H G L N L E E A A R Y M R S L K V P A T V S V S S P D A V T A Y N G Y L T S S S K T P E E H F I E T I S L A G S Y K D W S Y 4762

12,820 12,840 12,860 12,880 12,900 12,920 12,940 12,960 12,980 13,000

proto Wuhan Translation ORF/CDS A L L S D L Q D L K W A R F P K S D G T G T I Y T E L E P P C R F V T D T P K G P K V K Y L Y F I K G L N N L N R G M V L G S L A A T

12,949

proto Alpha Translation ORF/CDS A L L S D L Q D L K W A R F P K S D G T G T I Y T E L E P P C R F V T D T P K G P K V K Y L Y F I K G L N N L N R G M V L G S L A A T

12,958

proto Beta Translation ORF/CDS A L L S D L Q D L K W A R F P K S D G T G T I Y T E L E P P C R F V T D T P K G P K V K Y L Y F I K G L N N L N R G M V L G S L A A T

12,969

proto Gamma Translation ORF/CDS A L L S D L Q D L K W A R F P K S D G T G T I Y T E L E P P C R F V T D T P K G P K V K Y L Y F I K G L N N L N R G M V L G S L A A T

12,958

proto Delta Translation ORF/CDS A L L S D L Q D L K W A R F P K S D G T G T I Y T E L E P P C R F V T D T P K G P K V K Y L Y F I K G L N N L N R G M V L G S L A A T

12,965

proto MuGH Translation ORF/CDS A L L S D L Q D L K W A R F P K S D G T G T I Y T E L E P P C R F V T D T P K G P K V K Y L Y F I K G L N N L N R G M V L G S L A A T

12,958

proto Omicron Translation ORF/CDS A L L S D L Q D L K W A R F P K S D G T G T I Y T E L E P P C R F V T D T P K G P K V K Y L Y F I K G L N N L N R G M V L G S L A A T

12,950

13,020 13,040 13,060 13,080 13,100 13,120 13,140 13,160 13,180 13,200

proto Wuhan Translation ORF/CDS G T A C G T C T A C A A G C T G A T T G C A A C A A G C T G C C G C A A T C A A C T G A T T A T T C T G T G A G A C T G C T A A A G C T A C A A A G T A T T A C T A G C T G G G G A C A A C A A T C A A T T G T G T A A G A C T T G T G T A C A C A C A C T G G T C A G G A A A C A A C G T T A C C A G G A A C C A A T

13,200

13,249

proto Alpha Translation ORF/CDS V R L Q A G N A T E V P A N S T V L S F C A F A V D A A K A Y K D Y L A S G G Q P I T N C V K M L C T H T G T G Q A I T V T P E A N M

13,149

proto Beta Translation ORF/CDS V R L Q A G N A T E V P A N S T V L S F C A F A V D A A K A Y K D Y L A S G G Q P I T N C V K M L C T H T G T G Q A I T V T P E A N M

13,166

proto Gamma Translation ORF/CDS V R L Q A G N A T E V P A N S T V L S F C A F A V D A A K A Y K D Y L A S G G Q P I T N C V K M L C T H T G T G Q A I T V T P E A N M

13,169

proto Delta Translation ORF/CDS V R L Q A G N A T E V P A N S T V L S F C A F A V D A A K A Y K D Y L A S G G Q P I T N C V K M L C T H T G T G Q A I T V T P E A N M

13,158

proto Lambda Translation ORF/CDS V R L Q A G N A T E V P A N S T V L S F C A F A V D A A K A Y K D Y L A S G G Q P I T N C V K M L C T H T G T G Q A I T V T P E A N M

13,165

proto MuGH Translation ORF/CDS V R L Q A G N A T E V P A N S T V L S F C A F A V D A A K A Y K D Y L A S G G Q P I T N C V K M L C T H T G T G Q A I T V T P E A N M

13,155

proto Omicron Translation ORF/CDS V R L Q A G N A T E V P A N S T V L S F C A F A V D A A K A Y K D Y L A S G G Q P I T N C V K M L C T H T G T G Q A I T V T P E A N M

13,150

13,220 13,240 13,260 13,280 13,300 13,320 13,340 13,360 13,380 13,400

proto Wuhan Translation ORF/CDS G G A T C A A G A C C T T G C T G C T G T G T G T G T G C C G C C T G C C A C A T A G C T C A A A T C T A A A G A C T T T G C A C T A A A A G C T A G T A T G C A A C T C T A C A C T T G C T A T C A C C C T G G G G T T T A C A C T A A A A C A C A G T T G T C C G C T G T G C G A A G G T T A T G C T G A T T

13,400

13,349

proto Alpha Translation ORF/CDS D Q E S F G G A S C C L Y C R C H I D H P N P K G F C D L K G K Y V Q I P T T C A N D P V G F T L K N T V C T V C G M W K G Y G C S

13,366

proto Beta Translation ORF/CDS D Q E S F G G A S C C L Y C R C H I D H P N P K G F C D L K G K Y V Q I P T T C A N D P V G F T L K N T V C T V C G M W K G Y G C S

13,369

proto Gamma Translation ORF/CDS D Q E S F G G A S C C L Y C R C H I D H P N P K G F C D L K G K Y V Q I P T T C A N D P V G F T L K N T V C T V C G M W K G Y G C S

13,358

proto Delta Translation ORF/CDS D Q E S F G G A S C C L Y C R C H I D H P N P K G F C D L K G K Y V Q I P T T C A N D P V G F T L K N T V C T V C G M W K G Y G C S

13,365

proto Lambda Translation ORF/CDS D Q E S F G G A S C C L Y C R C H I D H P N P K G F C D L K G K Y V Q I P T T C A N D P V G F T L K N T V C T V C G M W K G Y G C S

13,355

proto MuGH Translation ORF/CDS D Q E S F G G A S C C L Y C R C H I D H P N P K G F C D L K G K Y V Q I P T T C A N D P V G F T L K N T V C T V C G M W K G Y G C S

13,350

proto Omicron Translation ORF/CDS D Q E S F G G A S C C L Y C R C H I D H P N P K G F C D L K G K Y V Q I P T T C A N D P V G F T L K N T V C T V C G M W K G Y G C S

13,350

13,420 13,440 13,460 13,480 13,500 13,520 13,540 13,560 13,580 13,600

proto Wuhan Translation ORF/CDS G T A T C A A C T C C G G A A C C A T G C T C A C T G A T G C A C A T C G T T T T A A A G C G G T T G C G C T T A A G C C G C T T A C A C C G C C G C C A C G G C A C T A G C T A G T G A T G C T A T A C A G G C C T T G A C A T C A A A G C C T G G T T T G A C A T A A A A C A C A G T T G T G A A A T C C T A A A A C T A A T T G T G C C T C C A A G

13,600

13,549

proto Alpha Translation ORF/CDS C D Q L R E P M L Q S A D A Q S F L N R V C G V S A A R L T P C G T G T S T D V V Y R A F D I Y N D K V A G F A K F L K T N C C R F Q

13,566

proto Beta Translation ORF/CDS C D Q L R E P M L Q S A D A Q S F L N R V C G V S A A R L T P C G T G T S T D V V Y R A F D I Y N D K V A G F A K F L K T N C C R F Q

13,569

proto Gamma Translation ORF/CDS C D Q L R E P M L Q S A D A Q S F L N R V C G V S A A R L T P C G T G T S T D V V Y R A F D I Y N D K V A G F A K F L K T N C C R F Q

13,558

proto Delta Translation ORF/CDS C D Q L R E P M L Q S A D A Q S F L N R V C G V S A A R L T P C G T G T S T D V V Y R A F D I Y N D K V A G F A K F L K T N C C R F Q

13,565

proto Lambda Translation ORF/CDS C D Q L R E P M L Q S A D A Q S F L N R V C G V S A A R L T P C G T G T S T D V V Y R A F D I Y N D K V A G F A K F L K T N C C R F Q

13,558

proto MuGH Translation ORF/CDS C D Q L R E P M L Q S A D A Q S F L N R V C G V S A A R L T P C G T G T S T D V V Y R A F D I Y N D K V A G F A K F L K T N C C R F Q

13,550

proto Omicron Translation ORF/CDS C D Q L R E P M L Q S A D A Q S F L N R V C G V S A A R L T P C G T G T S T D V V Y R A F D I Y N D K V A G F A K F L K T N C C R F Q

13,550

13,620 13,640 13,660 13,680 13,700 13,720 13,740 13,760 13,780 13,800

proto Wuhan Translation ORF/CDS A A A A G C A A G A G T G A C A A T T A A T T G T T C T A C T T T G A T T A A G A G A C A C T T C T A C T A C C A C C A T G A A G A A A A T T A T A A T T A C T T A A G A G T T C C A C C T T G C T A A A C A C T C T T T A G T T T A G A T A C A G C T G A C T G G T A C C A C A T A T A C T G C C A C G T C T T A A A T A C A A A T G

13,800

13,749

proto Alpha Translation ORF/CDS E K D E D D N L I D S Y F V V K R H T F S N Y Q H E E T I Y N L L K D C P A V A K H D F F K F R I D G D M V P H I S R Q R L T K Y T M

13,726

proto Beta Translation ORF/CDS E K D E D D N L I D S Y F V V K R H T F S N Y Q H E E T I Y N L L K D C P A V A K H D F F K F R I D G D M V P H I S R Q R L T K Y T M

13,769

proto Gamma Translation ORF/CDS E K D E D D N L I D S Y F V V K R H T F S N Y Q H E E T I Y N L L K D C P A V A K H D F F K F R I D G D M V P H I S R Q R L T K Y T M

13,758

proto Delta Translation ORF/CDS E K D E D D N L I D S Y F V V K R H T F S N Y Q H E E T I Y N L L K D C P A V A K H D F F K F R I D G D M V P H I S R Q R L T K Y T M

13,765

proto Lambda Translation ORF/CDS E K D E D D N L I D S Y F V V K R H T F S N Y Q H E E T I Y N L L K D C P A V A K H D F F K F R I D G D M V P H I S R Q R L T K Y T M

13,758

proto MuGH Translation ORF/CDS E K D E D D N L I D S Y F V V K R H T F S N Y Q H E E T I Y N L L K D C P A V A K H D F F K F R I D G D M V P H I S R Q R L T K Y T M

13,750

proto Omicron Translation ORF/CDS E K D E D D N L I D S Y F V V K R H T F S N Y Q H E E T I Y N L L K D C P A V A K H D F F K F R I D G D M V P H I S R Q R L T K Y T M

13,750

13,820 13,840 13,860 13,880 13,900 13,920 13,940 13,960 13,980 14,000

proto Wuhan Translation ORF/CDS G C A C C A C T G C T A G C T T A A G C A T T G T G A A G G T A T T G T C A C A C A T T A A A A A A A C T T G T G C A T A C A A A T T G T G T A T T A T T C A A A A A C A C A G A C T G A T A T T T T G A G A A C C A G A T A T T A C C G T A T T A C C G T A T T A C C G T A T T A C C G T A T T A C C G T A T T A C C G T A T T A C C A A C A T A C A C A T G

14,000

13,949

proto Alpha Translation ORF/CDS A D L V Y A L R H F D E G N C D T L K E I L V T Y N C C D D D Y F N K K D W Y D F V E N P D I L R V Y A N L G E R V R Q A L L K T V Q

13,966

proto Beta Translation ORF/CDS A D L V Y A L R H F D E G N C D T L K E I L V T Y N C C D D D Y F N K K D W Y D F V E N P D I L R V Y A N L G E R V R Q A L L K T V Q

13,969

proto Gamma Translation ORF/CDS A D L V Y A L R H F D E G N C D T L K E I L V T Y N C C D D D Y F N K K D W Y D F V E N P D I L R V Y A N L G E R V R Q A L L K T V Q

13,958

proto Delta Translation ORF/CDS A D L V Y A L R H F D E G N C D T L K E I L V T Y N C C D D D Y F N K K D W Y D F V E N P D I L R V Y A N L G E R V R Q A L L K T V Q

13,965

proto Lambda Translation ORF/CDS A D L V Y A L R H F D E G N C D T L K E I L V T Y N C C D D D Y F N K K D W Y D F V E N P D I L R V Y A N L G E R V R Q A L L K T V Q

13,958

proto MuGH Translation ORF/CDS A D L V Y A L R H F D E G N C D T L K E I L V T Y N C C D D D Y F N K K D W Y D F V E N P D I L R V Y A N L G E R V R Q A L L K T V Q

13,950

proto Omicron Translation ORF/CDS A D L V Y A L R H F D E G N C D T L K E I L V T Y N C C D D D Y F N K K D W Y D F V E N P D I L R V Y A N L G E R V R Q A L L K T V Q

14,000

14,020 14,040 14,060 14,080 14,100 14,120 14,140 14,160 14,180 14,200

proto Wuhan Translation ORF/CDS A T T C T G G C A T C C G A A A G T G G T T T G T G C T G A C A T T A G A A T C A A G A A C T T C A A A A A A A A A T T A T A A T T A C T T A A G A G T T C C A C C T T G C T A A A C A C T C T T T A G T T T A G A T A C A G C T G A C T G G T A C C A C A T A T A C T G C C A C G T C T T A A A T A C A A A T G

14,200

14,149

proto Alpha Translation ORF/CDS F C D A M R N A G I V G V L T L D N Q D L N G N W Y D F G D F I Q T T P G S G V P V V D S Y S L L M P I L L T L T R A L T A E S H V

14,166

proto Beta Translation ORF/CDS F C D A M R N A G I V G V L T L D N Q D L N G N W Y D F G D F I Q T T P G S G V P V V D S Y S L L M P I L L T L T R A L T A E S H V

14,169

proto Gamma Translation ORF/CDS F C D A M R N A G I V G V L T L D N Q D L N G N W Y D F G D F I Q T T P G S G V P V V D S Y S L L M P I L L T L T R A L T A E S H V

14,158

proto Delta Translation ORF/CDS F C D A M R N A G I V G V L T L D N Q D L N G N W Y D F G D F I Q T T P G S G V P V V D S Y S L L M P I L L T L T R A L T A E S H V

14,165

proto Lambda Translation ORF/CDS F C D A M R N A G I V G V L T L D N Q D L N G N W Y D F G D F I Q T T P G S G V P V V D S Y S L L M P I L L T L T R A L T A E S H V

14,158

proto MuGH Translation ORF/CDS F C D A M R N A G I V G V L T L D N Q D L N G N W Y D F G D F I Q T T P G S G V P V V D S Y S L L M P I L L T L T R A L T A E S H V

14,150

proto Omicron Translation ORF/CDS F C D A M R N A G I V G V L T L D N Q D L N G N W Y D F G D F I Q T T P G S G V P V V D S Y S L L M P I L L T L T R A L T A E S H V

14,150

14,220 14,240 14,260 14,280 14,300 14,320 14,340 14,360 14,380 14,400

proto Wuhan Translation ORF/CDS A C T G A C T A A A A C C C T A C A T T A C T G G A T T G T T A A A T A G C T C A A G G T T A A A C C T T T G A C C T T A T T A A A T T G G A T C A C A C A C C A A A T T C T T A A C T T T G G A T C A G A T C A A T T C G A T T G T G C A A A T T A A T G T T A T T C T A C A G T T C C C A C T A C A

14,400

14,349

proto Alpha Translation ORF/CDS D T D L T K P Y I K W D L L K Y D F T E E R L K L F D R Y F K Y W D Q T Y H P N C V N C L D D R C I L H C A N F N V L F S T V F P L T

14,366

proto Beta Translation ORF/CDS D T D L T K P Y I K W D L L K Y D F T E E R L K L F D R Y F K Y W D Q T Y H P N C V N C L D D R C I L H C A N F N V L F S T V F P L T

14,369

proto Gamma Translation ORF/CDS D T D L T K P Y I K W D L L K Y D F T E E R L K L F D R Y F K Y W D Q T Y H P N C V N C L D D R C I L H C A N F N V L F S T V F P L T

14,358

proto Delta Translation ORF/CDS D T D L T K P Y I K W D L L K Y D F T E E R L K L F D R Y F K Y W D Q T Y H P N C V N C L D D R C I L H C A N F N V L F S T V F P L T

14,365

proto Lambda Translation ORF/CDS D T D L T K P Y I K W D L L K Y D F T E E R L K L F D R Y F K Y W D Q T Y H P N C V N C L D D R C I L H C A N F N V L F S T V F P L T

14,358

proto MuGH Translation ORF/CDS D T D L T K P Y I K W D L L K Y D F T E E R L K L F D R Y F K Y W D Q T Y H P N C V N C L D D R C I L H C A N F N V L F S T V F P L T

14,350

proto Omicron Translation ORF/CDS D T D L T K P Y I K W D L L K Y D F T E E R L K L F D R Y F K Y W D Q T Y H P N C V N C L D D R C I L H C A N F N V L F S T V F P L T

14,350

17,620 17,640 17,660 17,680 17,700 17,720 17,740 17,760 17,780 17,800

proto Wuhan Translation ORF/CDS TAAGCTTAAAGCACATAAAGCAACACTCAATCGCTTTAAAGTGTTTTAAAGGCTGTTTACAGCGATGATGTTTCATCGCAATTAACAGCGCAAAATAGGCGTGAAGAGAAATCCTACACAGTAACTCGCTGGAGAAAGCTCTTTATTCACCTATAATACACAGAGCTGACCTCAAAAGTTT 18000

proto Alpha Translation ORF/CDS K L K A H K D K S A Q C F K M F Y K G V I T H D V S S A I N R P Q I G V V R E F L T R N P A W R K A V F I S P Y N S Q N A V A S K I 17749

proto Beta Translation ORF/CDS K L K A H K D K S A Q C F K M F Y K G V I T H D V S S A I N R P Q I G V V R E F L T R N P A W R K A V F I S P Y N S Q N A V A S K I 17766

proto Gamma Translation ORF/CDS K L K A H K D K S A Q C F K M F Y K G V I T H D V S S A I N R P Q I G V V R E F L T R N P A W R K A V F I S P Y N S Q N A V A S K I 17769

proto Delta Translation ORF/CDS K L K A H K D K S A Q C F K M F Y K G V I T H D V S S A I N R P Q I G V V R E F L T R N P A W R K A V F I S P Y N S Q N A V A S K I 17758

proto Lambda Translation ORF/CDS K L K A H K D K S A Q C F K M F Y K G V I T H D V S S A I N R P Q I G V V R E F L T R N P A W R K A V F I S P Y N S Q N A V A S K I 17765

proto MuGH Translation ORF/CDS K L K A H K D K S A Q C F K M F Y K G V I T H D V S S A I N R P Q I G V V R E F L T R N P A W R K A V F I S P Y N S Q N A V A S K I 17758

proto Omicron Translation ORF/CDS K L K A H K D K S A Q C F K M F Y K G V I T H D V S S A I N R P Q I G V V R E F L T R N P A W R K A V F I S P Y N S Q N A V A S K I 17750

18,200 18,220 18,240 18,260 18,280 18,300 18,320 18,340 18,360 18,380 18,400

proto Wuhan Translation ORF/CDS TGGCACTAACCACTCAACTGCTTTCATCACAGGCTCAGAAATGACTGATCTGATCTCACTCAAACTCAAAAGCTCACTCTGTAATTAACAGAGTAAATGCTTTCATCACAGCAAGTACGCTATTCGATACAGCAAGTCTGATACAGCAAGCTTTATGACAAAGTTCGAAATTCACAGCTTGAAGTT 18000

proto Alpha Translation ORF/CDS L G L P T Q T V D S S Q G S E Y D Y V I F T Q T T E T A H S C N V N R F N V A I T R A K V G I L C I M S D R D L Y D K L Q F T S L E I 17949

proto Beta Translation ORF/CDS L G L P T Q T V D S S Q G S E Y D Y V I F T Q T T E T A H S C N V N R F N V A I T R A K V G I L C I M S D R D L Y D K L Q F T S L E I 17966

proto Gamma Translation ORF/CDS L G L P T Q T V D S S Q G S E Y D Y V I F T Q T T E T A H S C N V N R F N V A I T R A K V G I L C I M S D R D L Y D K L Q F T S L E I 17969

proto Delta Translation ORF/CDS L G L P T Q T V D S S Q G S E Y D Y V I F T Q T T E T A H S C N V N R F N V A I T R A K V G I L C I M S D R D L Y D K L Q F T S L E I 17958

proto Lambda Translation ORF/CDS L G L P T Q T V D S S Q G S E Y D Y V I F T Q T T E T A H S C N V N R F N V A I T R A K V G I L C I M S D R D L Y D K L Q F T S L E I 17965

proto MuGH Translation ORF/CDS L G L P T Q T V D S S Q G S E Y D Y V I F T Q T T E T A H S C N V N R F N V A I T R A K V G I L C I M S D R D L Y D K L Q F T S L E I 17958

proto Omicron Translation ORF/CDS L G L P T Q T V D S S Q G S E Y D Y V I F T Q T T E T A H S C N V N R F N V A I T R A K V G I L C I M S D R D L Y D K L Q F T S L E I 17950

18,420 18,440 18,460 18,480 18,500 18,520 18,540 18,560 18,580 18,600

proto Wuhan Translation ORF/CDS CACTAGGAATCTGGCAACTTACAGACTGAAATGTTACAGCACTTTAAAGTGTAGTAAGGTAATCACTGGCTTACTCTACAGGCACTCACTCACTGCTGACACTAAATCAAACTCAAGGTTTGTGCTGACACTGGCTACTAGGACATCACTATAGAACTCACTCTCATAT 18200

proto Alpha Translation ORF/CDS P R R N V A T L Q A E N V T G L F K D C S K V I T G L H P T Q A P T H L S V D T K F K T E G L C V D I P G I P K D M T Y R R L I S M M 18149

proto Beta Translation ORF/CDS P R R N V A T L Q A E N V T G L F K D C S K V I T G L H P T Q A P T H L S V D T K F K T E G L C V D I P G I P K D M T Y R R L I S M M 18166

proto Gamma Translation ORF/CDS P R R N V A T L Q A E N V T G L F K D C S K V I T G L H P T Q A P T H L S V D T K F K T E G L C V D I P G I P K D M T Y R R L I S M M 18169

proto Delta Translation ORF/CDS P R R N V A T L Q A E N V T G L F K D C S K V I T G L H P T Q A P T H L S V D T K F K T E G L C V D I P G I P K D M T Y R R L I S M M 18158

proto Lambda Translation ORF/CDS P R R N V A T L Q A E N V T G L F K D C S K V I T G L H P T Q A P T H L S V D T K F K T E G L C V D I P G I P K D M T Y R R L I S M M 18165

proto MuGH Translation ORF/CDS P R R N V A T L Q A E N V T G L F K D C S K V I T G L H P T Q A P T H L S V D T K F K T E G L C V D I P G I P K D M T Y R R L I S M M 18158

proto Omicron Translation ORF/CDS P R R N V A T L Q A E N V T G L F K D C S K V I T G L H P T Q A P T H L S V D T K F K T E G L C V D I P G I P K D M T Y R R L I S M M 18150

18,620 18,640 18,660 18,680 18,700 18,720 18,740 18,760 18,780 18,800

proto Wuhan Translation ORF/CDS GGGTTTAAATCAATTAACAAGTAAAGGTTACCTCAACTGTTTATCACCCGGCAAGAGCTAAGAACACTACGCTGATGGCTCGATGTCGAGGCTGTCATCTACTAGAGCAAGCTGTTGGTACCAATTTACCTTTACAGCTAGGTTTCTTACAGGTTTAACTCACTGCTCACTACAGGTTATG 18400

proto Alpha Translation ORF/CDS G F K M N Y Q V N G Y P N M F I T R E E A I R H V R A W I G F D V E G C H A T R E A V G T N L P L Q L G F S T G V N L V A V P T G Y 18349

proto Beta Translation ORF/CDS G F K M N Y Q V N G Y P N M F I T R E E A I R H V R A W I G F D V E G C H A T R E A V G T N L P L Q L G F S T G V N L V A V P T G Y 18366

proto Gamma Translation ORF/CDS G F K M N Y Q V N G Y P N M F I T R E E A I R H V R A W I G F D V E G C H A T R E A V G T N L P L Q L G F S T G V N L V A V P T G Y 18369

proto Delta Translation ORF/CDS G F K M N Y Q V N G Y P N M F I T R E E A I R H V R A W I G F D V E G C H A T R E A V G T N L P L Q L G F S T G V N L V A V P T G Y 18358

proto Lambda Translation ORF/CDS G F K M N Y Q V N G Y P N M F I T R E E A I R H V R A W I G F D V E G C H A T R E A V G T N L P L Q L G F S T G V N L V A V P T G Y 18365

proto MuGH Translation ORF/CDS G F K M N Y Q V N G Y P N M F I T R E E A I R H V R A W I G F D V E G C H A T R E A V G T N L P L Q L G F S T G V N L V A V P T G Y 18358

proto Omicron Translation ORF/CDS G F K M N Y Q V N G Y P N M F I T R E E A I R H V R A W I G F D V E G C H A T R E A V G T N L P L Q L G F S T G V N L V A V P T G Y 18350

18,820 18,840 18,860 18,880 18,900 18,920 18,940 18,960 18,980 19,000

proto Wuhan Translation ORF/CDS TTGATACACCTAATAACAGACTTTTCCAGACTAGTCTAAACACCGCTGGAGTCAATTAACACCTCATACACTTGTACAAAGCACTCTGTTGAAGTGTAGCGTATGACAAATTTGACAAATTTAAGTACACACTAAAACTCTCTGACAGACTCGTATTTGTTTATGGCAAGCTGCTTTCAG 18600

proto Alpha Translation ORF/CDS V D T P N N T D F S R V S A K P P P G D Q F K H L I P L M Y K G L P W N V V R I K I V Q M L S D T L K N L S D R V V F V L W A H G F E 18549

proto Beta Translation ORF/CDS V D T P N N T D F S R V S A K P P P G D Q F K H L I P L M Y K G L P W N V V R I K I V Q M L S D T L K N L S D R V V F V L W A H G F E 18566

proto Gamma Translation ORF/CDS V D T P N N T D F S R V S A K P P P G D Q F K H L I P L M Y K G L P W N V V R I K I V Q M L S D T L K N L S D R V V F V L W A H G F E 18569

proto Delta Translation ORF/CDS V D T P N N T D F S R V S A K P P P G D Q F K H L I P L M Y K G L P W N V V R I K I V Q M L S D T L K N L S D R V V F V L W A H G F E 18558

proto Lambda Translation ORF/CDS V D T P N N T D F S R V S A K P P P G D Q F K H L I P L M Y K G L P W N V V R I K I V Q M L S D T L K N L S D R V V F V L W A H G F E 18565

proto MuGH Translation ORF/CDS V D T P N N T D F S R V S A K P P P G D Q F K H L I P L M Y K G L P W N V V R I K I V Q M L S D T L K N L S D R V V F V L W A H G F E 18558

proto Omicron Translation ORF/CDS V D T P N N T D F S R V S A K P P P G D Q F K H L I P L M Y K G L P W N V V R I K I V Q M L S D T L K N L S D R V V F V L W A H G F E 18550

18,920 18,940 18,960 18,980 18,700 18,720 18,740 18,760 18,780 18,800

proto Wuhan Translation ORF/CDS TTGACTCTTAAGTATTTGAAATAGACACTGACCGCACTTGTCTATGATGACAGCTCCACACTGTTTCACTGCTCAGACACTTGGCTTGGACTCTTAACTTGGATTTGATGCTTAACTGCTGAACTGAAGATTTAGCTGGCTTCTAGAGAAAGCTCAACACTGGTGTAAAGCTGATATTAGACACA 18800

proto Alpha Translation ORF/CDS L T S M K Y F V K I G P E R T C C L C D R R A T C F S T A S D T Y A C W H H S I G F D Y V Y N P P F M I D V Q Q W G F T G N L Q S N H D 18749

proto Beta Translation ORF/CDS L T S M K Y F V K I G P E R T C C L C D R R A T C F S T A S D T Y A C W H H S I G F D Y V Y N P P F M I D V Q Q W G F T G N L Q S N H D 18766

proto Gamma Translation ORF/CDS L T S M K Y F V K I G P E R T C C L C D R R A T C F S T A S D T Y A C W H H S I G F D Y V Y N P P F M I D V Q Q W G F T G N L Q S N H D 18769

proto Delta Translation ORF/CDS L T S M K Y F V K I G P E R T C C L C D R R A T C F S T A S D T Y A C W H H S I G F D Y V Y N P P F M I D V Q Q W G F T G N L Q S N H D 18758

proto Lambda Translation ORF/CDS L T S M K Y F V K I G P E R T C C L C D R R A T C F S T A S D T Y A C W H H S I G F D Y V Y N P P F M I D V Q Q W G F T G N L Q S N H D 18765

proto MuGH Translation ORF/CDS L T S M K Y F V K I G P E R T C C L C D R R A T C F S T A S D T Y A C W H H S I G F D Y V Y N P P F M I D V Q Q W G F T G N L Q S N H D 18758

proto Omicron Translation ORF/CDS L T S M K Y F V K I G P E R T C C L C D R R A T C F S T A S D T Y A C W H H S I G F D Y V Y N P P F M I D V Q Q W G F T G N L Q S N H D 18750

18,920 18,940 18,960 18,980 19,000 19,020 19,040 19,060 19,080 19,100

proto Wuhan Translation ORF/CDS TCTGTATGCTCAAGTCTGTAATGACACTGAGTCTGCTGGAATCATGACTAGTGTCTGACTGCTCCAGCAAGCTTGTGTAAGTGTGACTGACTGATGAAATCTCTAATGCTGAACTGAAGATTTAGCTGGCTTCTAGAGAAAGCTCAACACTGGTGTAAAGCTGATATTAGACACA 19000

proto Alpha Translation ORF/CDS L Y C Q V H G N A H V A S C D A I M T R C L A V H E C F V K R V D W T I E Y P I I G D E L K I N A A C R K V Q H M V V K A A L L A D 18949

proto Beta Translation ORF/CDS L Y C Q V H G N A H V A S C D A I M T R C L A V H E C F V K R V D W T I E Y P I I G D E L K I N A A C R K V Q H M V V K A A L L A D 18966

proto Gamma Translation ORF/CDS L Y C Q V H G N A H V A S C D A I M T R C L A V H E C F V K R V D W T I E Y P I I G D E L K I N A A C R K V Q H M V V K A A L L A D 18969

proto Delta Translation ORF/CDS L Y C Q V H G N A H V A S C D A I M T R C L A V H E C F V K R V D W T I E Y P I I G D E L K I N A A C R K V Q H M V V K A A L L A D 18958

proto Lambda Translation ORF/CDS L Y C Q V H G N A H V A S C D A I M T R C L A V H E C F V K R V D W T I E Y P I I G D E L K I N A A C R K V Q H M V V K A A L L A D 18965

proto MuGH Translation ORF/CDS L Y C Q V H G N A H V A S C D A I M T R C L A V H E C F V K R V D W T I E Y P I I G D E L K I N A A C R K V Q H M V V K A A L L A D 18958

proto Omicron Translation ORF/CDS L Y C Q V H G N A H V A S C D A I M T R C L A V H E C F V K R V D W T I E Y P I I G D E L K I N A A C R K V Q H M V V K A A L L A D 18950

19,020 19,040 19,060 19,080 19,100 19,120 19,140 19,160 19,180 19,200

proto Wuhan Translation ORF/CDS AATTCCCTTCTCACAGACTGGTAACTCAAGCTTTAAGTGTGATCACTCAAGCTGATGACAGCAAGCTTAAATAGAAATTAATCTTCTTATGCTCACACTCTCACAAATTCACAGCTGGTGTGCTTCTTATGCAATGCGATGACAG 19200

proto Alpha Translation ORF/CDS K F P V L H D I G N P K A I K C V P Q A D V E W K F Y D A Q P C S D K A Y K I E E L F Y S Y A T H S D K F T D G V C L F W N C N V D R 19149

proto Beta Translation ORF/CDS K F P V L H D I G N P K A I K C V P Q A D V E W K F Y D A Q P C S D K A Y K I E E L F Y S Y A T H S D K F T D G V C L F W N C N V D R 19166

proto Gamma Translation ORF/CDS K F P V L H D I G N P K A I K C V P Q A D V E W K F Y D A Q P C S D K A Y K I E E L F Y S Y A T H S D K F T D G V C L F W N C N V D R 19169

proto Delta Translation ORF/CDS K F P V L H D I G N P K A I K C V P Q A D V E W K F Y D A Q P C S D K A Y K I E E L F Y S Y A T H S D K F T D G V C L F W N C N V D R 19158

proto Lambda Translation ORF/CDS K F P V L H D I G N P K A I K C V P Q A D V E W K F Y D A Q P C S D K A Y K I E E L F Y S Y A T H S D K F T D G V C L F W N C N V D R 19165

proto MuGH Translation ORF/CDS K F P V L H D I G N P K A I K C V P Q A D V E W K F Y D A Q P C S D K A Y K I E E L F Y S Y A T H S D K F T D G V C L F W N C N V D R 19158

proto Omicron Translation ORF/CDS K F P V L H D I G N P K A I K C V P Q A D V E W K F Y D A Q P C S D K A Y K I E E L F Y S Y A T H S D K F T D G V C L F W N C N V D R 19150

	28,820	28,840	28,860	28,880	28,900	28,920	28,940	28,960	28,980	29,000
proto Wuhan	GGAGCAGAGCGGGAGTCAAGCTCTCTGCTTCCTACAGTCCGCAACAGTTCAGAAATCACTCCAGGCAGCAGTGGGAACTCTCTCTGAGAACTGGCGGCTGATGCTGCTTCTGCTGCTGACAGATGAAACAGCTTGAGAGCAAAATCTGCTGAAAGCCACACAA									
Translation ORF/CDS	G S R G G S Q A S S R S S S R S R N S S R N S T P G S S R G T S P A R M A G N G G D A A L A L L L L D R L N Q L E S K M S G K G Q Q Q									
proto Alpha	G S R G G S Q A S S R S S S R S R N S S R N S T P G S S R G T S P A R M A G N G G D A A L A L L L L D R L N Q L E S K M S G K G Q Q Q									
Translation ORF/CDS	G S R G G S Q A S S R S S S R S R N S S R N S T P G S S R G T S P A R M A G N G G D A A L A L L L L D R L N Q L E S K M S G K G Q Q Q									
proto Beta	G S R G G S Q A S S R S S S R S R N S S R N S T P G S S R G T S P A R M A G N G G D A A L A L L L L D R L N Q L E S K M S G K G Q Q Q									
Translation ORF/CDS	G S R G G S Q A S S R S S S R S R N S S R N S T P G S S R G T S P A R M A G N G G D A A L A L L L L D R L N Q L E S K M S G K G Q Q Q									
proto Gamma	G S R G G S Q A S S R S S S R S R N S S R N S T P G S S R G T S P A R M A G N G G D A A L A L L L L D R L N Q L E S K M S G K G Q Q Q									
Translation ORF/CDS	G S R G G S Q A S S R S S S R S R N S S R N S T P G S S R G T S P A R M A G N G G D A A L A L L L L D R L N Q L E S K M S G K G Q Q Q									
proto Delta	G S R G G S Q A S S R S S S R S R N S S R N S T P G S S R G T S P A R M A G N G G D A A L A L L L L D R L N Q L E S K M S G K G Q Q Q									
Translation ORF/CDS	G S R G G S Q A S S R S S S R S R N S S R N S T P G S S R G T S P A R M A G N G G D A A L A L L L L D R L N Q L E S K M S G K G Q Q Q									
proto Lambda	G S R G G S Q A S S R S S S R S R N S S R N S T P G S S R G T S P A R M A G N G G D A A L A L L L L D R L N Q L E S K M S G K G Q Q Q									
Translation ORF/CDS	G S R G G S Q A S S R S S S R S R N S S R N S T P G S S R G T S P A R M A G N G G D A A L A L L L L D R L N Q L E S K M S G K G Q Q Q									
proto MuGH	G S R G G S Q A S S R S S S R S R N S S R N S T P G S S R G T S P A R M A G N G G D A A L A L L L L D R L N Q L E S K M S G K G Q Q Q									
Translation ORF/CDS	G S R G G S Q A S S R S S S R S R N S S R N S T P G S S R G T S P A R M A G N G G D A A L A L L L L D R L N Q L E S K M S G K G Q Q Q									
proto Omicron	G S R G G S Q A S S R S S S R S R N S S R N S T P G S S R G T S P A R M A G N G G D A A L A L L L L D R L N Q L E S K M S G K G Q Q Q									
Translation ORF/CDS	G S R G G S Q A S S R S S S R S R N S S R N S T P G S S R G T S P A R M A G N G G D A A L A L L L L D R L N Q L E S K M S G K G Q Q Q									
proto Wuhan	28,920	28,940	28,960	28,980	29,000	29,020	29,040	29,060	29,080	29,100
Translation ORF/CDS	CAAGGCCAACTGCTCACTAAGAAATCTGCTGAGGCTCTAAGAGGCTCGGCAAAAGCTCCACTAAGACTACAACTGTAACCAAGCTTGGCGAGCCTGGCCAGCAAAACCAAGAAATTTGGGGACAGCAAACTAATCAGACAAAGCACTGATACAAACATTTGCCCAAAATTCACAATTTGC									
proto Alpha	Q G Q T V T K K S A A E A S K K P R Q K R T A T K A Y N V T Q A F G R R G P E Q T Q G N F G D Q E L I R Q G T D Y K H W P Q I A Q F A									
Translation ORF/CDS	Q G Q T V T K K S A A E A S K K P R Q K R T A T K A Y N V T Q A F G R R G P E Q T Q G N F G D Q E L I R Q G T D Y K H W P Q I A Q F A									
proto Beta	Q G Q T V T K K S A A E A S K K P R Q K R T A T K A Y N V T Q A F G R R G P E Q T Q G N F G D Q E L I R Q G T D Y K H W P Q I A Q F A									
Translation ORF/CDS	Q G Q T V T K K S A A E A S K K P R Q K R T A T K A Y N V T Q A F G R R G P E Q T Q G N F G D Q E L I R Q G T D Y K H W P Q I A Q F A									
proto Gamma	Q G Q T V T K K S A A E A S K K P R Q K R T A T K A Y N V T Q A F G R R G P E Q T Q G N F G D Q E L I R Q G T D Y K H W P Q I A Q F A									
Translation ORF/CDS	Q G Q T V T K K S A A E A S K K P R Q K R T A T K A Y N V T Q A F G R R G P E Q T Q G N F G D Q E L I R Q G T D Y K H W P Q I A Q F A									
proto Delta	Q G Q T V T K K S A A E A S K K P R Q K R T A T K A Y N V T Q A F G R R G P E Q T Q G N F G D Q E L I R Q G T D Y K H W P Q I A Q F A									
Translation ORF/CDS	Q G Q T V T K K S A A E A S K K P R Q K R T A T K A Y N V T Q A F G R R G P E Q T Q G N F G D Q E L I R Q G T D Y K H W P Q I A Q F A									
proto Lambda	Q G Q T V T K K S A A E A S K K P R Q K R T A T K A Y N V T Q A F G R R G P E Q T Q G N F G D Q E L I R Q G T D Y K H W P Q I A Q F A									
Translation ORF/CDS	Q G Q T V T K K S A A E A S K K P R Q K R T A T K A Y N V T Q A F G R R G P E Q T Q G N F G D Q E L I R Q G T D Y K H W P Q I A Q F A									
proto MuGH	Q G Q T V T K K S A A E A S K K P R Q K R T A T K A Y N V T Q A F G R R G P E Q T Q G N F G D Q E L I R Q G T D Y K H W P Q I A Q F A									
Translation ORF/CDS	Q G Q T V T K K S A A E A S K K P R Q K R T A T K A Y N V T Q A F G R R G P E Q T Q G N F G D Q E L I R Q G T D Y K H W P Q I A Q F A									
proto Omicron	Q G Q T V T K K S A A E A S K K P R Q K R T A T K A Y N V T Q A F G R R G P E Q T Q G N F G D Q E L I R Q G T D Y K H W P Q I A Q F A									
Translation ORF/CDS	Q G Q T V T K K S A A E A S K K P R Q K R T A T K A Y N V T Q A F G R R G P E Q T Q G N F G D Q E L I R Q G T D Y K H W P Q I A Q F A									
proto Wuhan	29,120	29,140	29,160	29,180	29,200	29,220	29,240	29,260	29,280	29,300
Translation ORF/CDS	CCCGAGCCTCACGCTTTCGGAATTCGGCATTGGATGAGTCCACACTCGGAACTGGTTCACCTACACAGTGGCACTCAAAATGGTGAACAATCCAAATTCAAAGTCAACTTTTCTGAAATAGCATATGACGCATACAAATCCCAACACAGCCTAAAGGACAAAGACAA									
proto Alpha	P S A S A F F G M S R I G M E V T P S G T W L T Y T G A I K L D D K D P N F K D Q V I L L N K H I D A Y K T F P P T E P K K D K K K									
Translation ORF/CDS	P S A S A F F G M S R I G M E V T P S G T W L T Y T G A I K L D D K D P N F K D Q V I L L N K H I D A Y K T F P P T E P K K D K K K									
proto Beta	P S A S A F F G M S R I G M E V T P S G T W L T Y T G A I K L D D K D P N F K D Q V I L L N K H I D A Y K T F P P T E P K K D K K K									
Translation ORF/CDS	P S A S A F F G M S R I G M E V T P S G T W L T Y T G A I K L D D K D P N F K D Q V I L L N K H I D A Y K T F P P T E P K K D K K K									
proto Gamma	P S A S A F F G M S R I G M E V T P S G T W L T Y T G A I K L D D K D P N F K D Q V I L L N K H I D A Y K T F P P T E P K K D K K K									
Translation ORF/CDS	P S A S A F F G M S R I G M E V T P S G T W L T Y T G A I K L D D K D P N F K D Q V I L L N K H I D A Y K T F P P T E P K K D K K K									
proto Delta	P S A S A F F G M S R I G M E V T P S G T W L T Y T G A I K L D D K D P N F K D Q V I L L N K H I D A Y K T F P P T E P K K D K K K									
Translation ORF/CDS	P S A S A F F G M S R I G M E V T P S G T W L T Y T G A I K L D D K D P N F K D Q V I L L N K H I D A Y K T F P P T E P K K D K K K									
proto Lambda	P S A S A F F G M S R I G M E V T P S G T W L T Y T G A I K L D D K D P N F K D Q V I L L N K H I D A Y K T F P P T E P K K D K K K									
Translation ORF/CDS	P S A S A F F G M S R I G M E V T P S G T W L T Y T G A I K L D D K D P N F K D Q V I L L N K H I D A Y K T F P P T E P K K D K K K									
proto MuGH	P S A S A F F G M S R I G M E V T P S G T W L T Y T G A I K L D D K D P N F K D Q V I L L N K H I D A Y K T F P P T E P K K D K K K									
Translation ORF/CDS	P S A S A F F G M S R I G M E V T P S G T W L T Y T G A I K L D D K D P N F K D Q V I L L N K H I D A Y K T F P P T E P K K D K K K									
proto Omicron	P S A S A F F G M S R I G M E V T P S G T W L T Y T G A I K L D D K D P N F K D Q V I L L N K H I D A Y K T F P P T E P K K D K K K									
Translation ORF/CDS	P S A S A F F G M S R I G M E V T P S G T W L T Y T G A I K L D D K D P N F K D Q V I L L N K H I D A Y K T F P P T E P K K D K K K									
proto Wuhan	29,320	29,340	29,360	29,380	29,400	29,420	29,440	29,460	29,480	29,500
Translation ORF/CDS	AGCGTGAACCTCAAGCTTACCGCAGAGCAGAGAAACAGCAAACTGACTCTTCTCTGCTGAGATTTGGATGATTCTCCAAACAATGCAACAATCCATGAGCAGGCTCACTCACTCAGGCTAACTCGCAGACACCAAGGAGAGGGCTATATAAAGCTTTTCGGTTTACGATA									
proto Alpha	K A D E T Q A L P Q R Q K K Q Q T V T L L P A A D L D D F S K Q L Q Q S M S S A D S T Q A									
Translation ORF/CDS	K A D E T Q A L P Q R Q K K Q Q T V T L L P A A D L D D F S K Q L Q Q S M S S A D S T Q A									
proto Beta	K A D E T Q A L P Q R Q K K Q Q T V T L L P A A D L D D F S K Q L Q Q S M S S A D S T Q A									
Translation ORF/CDS	K A D E T Q A L P Q R Q K K Q Q T V T L L P A A D L D D F S K Q L Q Q S M S S A D S T Q A									
proto Gamma	K A D E T Q A L P Q R Q K K Q Q T V T L L P A A D L D D F S K Q L Q Q S M S S A D S T Q A									
Translation ORF/CDS	K A D E T Q A L P Q R Q K K Q Q T V T L L P A A D L D D F S K Q L Q Q S M S S A D S T Q A									
proto Delta	K A D E T Q A L P Q R Q K K Q Q T V T L L P A A D L D D F S K Q L Q Q S M S S A D S T Q A									
Translation ORF/CDS	K A D E T Q A L P Q R Q K K Q Q T V T L L P A A D L D D F S K Q L Q Q S M S S A D S T Q A									
proto Lambda	K A D E T Q A L P Q R Q K K Q Q T V T L L P A A D L D D F S K Q L Q Q S M S S A D S T Q A									
Translation ORF/CDS	K A D E T Q A L P Q R Q K K Q Q T V T L L P A A D L D D F S K Q L Q Q S M S S A D S T Q A									
proto MuGH	K A D E T Q A L P Q R Q K K Q Q T V T L L P A A D L D D F S K Q L Q Q S M S S A D S T Q A									
Translation ORF/CDS	K A D E T Q A L P Q R Q K K Q Q T V T L L P A A D L D D F S K Q L Q Q S M S S A D S T Q A									
proto Omicron	K A D E T Q A L P Q R Q K K Q Q T V T L L P A A D L D D F S K Q L Q Q S M S S A D S T Q A									
Translation ORF/CDS	K A D E T Q A L P Q R Q K K Q Q T V T L L P A A D L D D F S K Q L Q Q S M S S A D S T Q A									
proto Wuhan	29,520	29,540	29,560	29,580	29,600	29,620	29,640	29,660	29,680	29,700
Translation ORF/CDS	TATAGTCACTCTTGTGAGAAATGATCTGTAAGTCACTAGGCAAGTGTGATTAATCTCACATAGCACTTTAATCAGTGTGAACATTAGGAGGACTGAAAGAGCCACCACTTTCCAGGAGCCAGCGGAGTACGATGACAGTGAACAATGCTAGGGAGAGCTCTATATGGA									
proto Alpha	Y S L L L C R M N S R N Y I A Q V D V V N F N L T									
Translation ORF/CDS	Y S L L L C R M N S R N Y I A Q V D V V N F N L T									
proto Beta	Y S L L L C R M N S R N Y I A Q V D V V N F N L T									
Translation ORF/CDS	Y S L L L C R M N S R N Y I A Q V D V V N F N L T									
proto Gamma	Y S L L L C R M N S R N Y I A Q V D V V N F N L T									
Translation ORF/CDS	Y S L L L C R M N S R N Y I A Q V D V V N F N L T									
proto Delta	Y S L L L C R M N S R N Y I A Q V D V V N F N L T									
Translation ORF/CDS	Y S L L L C R M N S R N Y I A Q V D V V N F N L T									
proto Lambda	Y S L L L C R M N S R N Y I A Q V D V V N F N L T									
Translation ORF/CDS	Y S L L L C R M N S R N Y I A Q V D V V N F N L T									
proto MuGH	Y S L L L C R M N S R N Y I A Q V D V V N F N L T									
Translation ORF/CDS	Y S L L L C R M N S R N Y I A Q V D V V N F N L T									
proto Omicron	Y S L L L C R M N S R N Y I A Q V D V V N F N L T									
Translation ORF/CDS	Y S L L L C R M N S R N Y I A Q V D V V N F N L T									
proto Wuhan	29,720	29,740	29,760	29,780	29,800	29,820	29,840	29,860	29,880	29,900
Translation ORF/CDS	AGAGCCCTAATGCTAAATTAATTTAGTGTCTCCCACTGATTTAATGACTCTTAGGAGCATGACAAAAAATAAAAAAAAAA 29878									
proto Alpha	29763									
Translation ORF/CDS	29763									
proto Beta	29782									
Translation ORF/CDS	29782									
proto Gamma	29788									
Translation ORF/CDS	29788									
proto Delta	29769									
Translation ORF/CDS	29769									
proto Lambda	29769									
Translation ORF/CDS	29769									
proto MuGH	29781									
Translation ORF/CDS	29781									
proto Omicron	29756									
Translation ORF/CDS	29756									